

"Development of Functional, Gluten-Free Bakery Products Enriched with Bioactive Components: Innovative Technological Solutions and Proven Gut Microbiota-Enhancing Effects"

The products developed within this project can be considered unique on both the domestic and international food markets, as bakery products with a similar composition and produced with the technologies we have developed are currently not available commercially. The specific proportions of bioactive components we have designed have never been used before, since they were developed through new and unique experiments.

Through our developments, we have expanded the wide range of health-protective products with foods whose beneficial physiological effects have been verified using in vitro model experiments. Such products are rarely available on the market, as manufacturers usually do not consider it essential to prove the positive biological effects of specific foods. With the large-scale production and market introduction of our newly developed food prototypes, we can reach a wide range of consumers with products that best match their tastes and health needs.

Based on our results, we created innovative bakery products that can be positioned as functional foods. We have been able to precisely demonstrate that our products significantly improve gut microbiota composition and reduce inflammatory symptoms; by positively modifying the colon's microflora, they can have therapeutic effects that improve patient outcomes. Through enrichment with bioactive components, our products promote health preservation, while also standing out in appearance and taste from competitors. This provides our company with a strong competitive advantage in this market segment. The actual health-protective effects were supported by complex, multifactorial biological model studies carried out as part of the project, thus confirming the specific benefits. The added value was achieved by using unique combinations of bioactive components and innovative technologies. In our experiments, we created health-promoting formulations through direct enrichment with collagen, anthocyanins, polysaccharide components extracted from lion's mane mushroom, prebiotics, and probiotics.

In the development of premium category, innovative, health-protective, gluten-free products, we implemented the following innovations:

1. Incorporating different collagen preparations into gluten-free pastries with optimized technology for different product matrices.
2. Developing pastries containing anthocyanin-carbohydrate blends.
3. Creating fillings containing lion's mane mushroom extract and red berry extracts, optimizing their effect on intestinal epithelial regeneration.

There is enormous demand for bakery products whose potential physiological benefits are proven with scientific rigor and credibility. In this respect, people with gluten intolerance, due to their associated health problems (primarily nutrient absorption and utilization issues), have an even greater need for such products. However, products that meet these criteria are rare in commercial circulation. Gluten-intolerant individuals, cancer patients, people with damaged intestinal epithelium, and those suffering from histamine intolerance (also associated with damaged intestinal epithelium) all represent significant market demand. In Hungary and neighboring countries, bakery products are the primary source of nutrition for the population and have the highest consumption

levels. Research indicates that demand for bakery products is less price-sensitive, and they remain the best-selling type of food, as they are among the most essential and most popular staples.

The quality of life of gluten-intolerant individuals can be significantly improved with scientifically designed products that provide nutrients typically found in conventional foods but missing from gluten-free alternatives. Current gluten-free products only partially meet the nutritional needs of gluten-intolerant individuals, as their development usually focuses on achieving sensory similarity to conventional, gluten-containing products and compatibility with existing manufacturing equipment. The resulting starch-based products lack exactly those substances necessary to mitigate the consequences of impaired absorption caused by gluten-triggered immune reactions damaging the intestinal epithelium. These include certain minerals, such as magnesium (already deficient in the Hungarian population's diet), water-soluble fibers (the specific nutrients of probiotic bacteria, whose absence promotes the proliferation of harmful bacteria that further irritate the sensitive intestinal wall), and antioxidant compounds (which help epithelial cells withstand digestive stress).

Today, there is growing demand for products whose actual physiological effects and expected health benefits are scientifically validated and credibly proven. Our new functional products are unique and fill a market gap in this respect, as we confirmed the bioavailability of our new product variations using an internationally novel in vitro digestion model system.

In vitro experiments using digestion models and Caco-2 cell culture, in collaboration with the Department of Pharmaceutical Technology, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Debrecen

For the scientific and technical foundation of our food product and technology developments, we applied the INFOGEST 2.0 protocol (Brodkorb et al., 2019) to study changes during digestion. This procedure is recognized internationally as the most suitable, as it was developed based on broad professional consensus, defining critical control steps that ensured our results were reproducible, robust, and accurately represented the quantity and quality of compounds released from different food matrices in the human body.

Our task was to determine how the bioactive compounds responsible for functionality change during digestion and how absorbable they are, depending on the food technology and composition. We considered that the complex processes occurring on the intestinal epithelium surface determine nutrient absorption, the normal functioning of the intestinal lining, and the activity of the gut-associated immune system, which plays a crucial role in overall immune defense.

Our goal was to reveal the molecular-level characteristics of the absorption of the ingredients and finished products used in functional food production, as well as to evaluate how manufacturing technology affected these characteristics. This provided precise information on the actual amount of our developed food components entering the human body and their expected influence on immune function.

In the Caco-2 cell culture model studies, we used pepsin–trypsin-digested gliadin and TNF- α to induce inflammatory processes. For both induction and plant extract treatments, we determined non-toxic concentrations, tested with an RTCA device before application to the cell model. Using the RTCA device, we measured the real-time cell index. In the case of toxicity, significant cell death and a decrease in cell index would have been observed. We confirmed that the chosen extract concentration had no toxic effect on Caco-2 cells.

The Caco-2 cells were cultured on a Transwell membrane, in contact with both an apical and a basal liquid compartment. On the apical side, PT-G + TNF- α treatment was applied for 24 hours, after which we examined the presumed protective effect of the polyphenol-rich plant extract on barrier function. Following treatments, we determined changes in transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) and FITC-dextran permeability. Both methods allowed the analysis of membrane barrier functions: TEER measured electrical resistance between the apical and basal surfaces, while the FITC-dextran test measured the permeability of a fluorescently labeled low molecular weight compound.

During inflammation induction, we observed the activation and rearrangement of proteins involved in cell-cell junction formation. Among the junctional proteins, we measured zonulin levels using flow cytometry in untreated samples, PT-G + TNF- α -induced samples, and PT-G + TNF- α + polyphenol-rich plant extract-treated samples.

Results:

In modeling celiac disease, we used gliadin (a wheat protein)-treated samples to observe cell responses typical of gluten intolerance. The gliadin treatment resulted in:

- Increased permeability between cells,
- Decreased levels of ZO-1 protein responsible for cell-cell connections,
- Activation of inflammatory processes (p65 protein translocated into the cell nucleus),
- Decreased membrane resistance (TEER), indicating damage to the cell layer.

In contrast, none of the tested dough samples (unfilled, protein-free, fruit-filled) caused similar negative changes:

- No significant increase in permeability between cells,
- No signs of inflammatory response (p65 did not enter the nucleus),
- Cell connections remained intact, with ZO-1 protein levels unchanged,
- Membrane resistance did not decrease significantly.

Conclusion: Gliadin triggered cell damage and inflammation characteristic of gluten intolerance, while the tested dough samples did not produce such effects and thus did not elicit celiac disease-specific responses.

Our products containing the improved, polyphenol-enriched filling:

- Plum pastry
- Sour cherry turnover

Sour cherry pie

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